

TYPES OF METHODS USED IN ELEMENTARY READING LESSONS

Zokirov Javohir G'aybullo o'g'li

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy of Termiz University of Economics and Service

Isaxonova O'g'ilshod Azizxon qizi

Student of Termiz University of Economics and Service

Phone: 998 77 051 19 29

Email: zjavohir6@gmail.com

Abstract: The types of oral methods, instructional methods, and practical methods used in elementary school reading lessons are discussed.

Key words: interactive, interactivity, interactive methods, oral methods, instructional methods, practical methods

Today, in schools, which are centers of knowledge, giving good education to young people who are gathering the necessary knowledge and skills to work effectively in different regions of our country, educating them to solve various problems of life also depends on the multifaceted work of teachers[1-3].

Effective use of methods and tools that respond to modern students, solving the problems of forming students' independent and creative thinking skills is of great importance in the organization of elementary school reading lessons.

There are also a number of pedagogues' works on interactive methods. In the methodical manual "Interactive methods: essence and application" created by Roziyeva D., Usmonova M., Khalikova Z., it is detailed about these teaching methods. The essence and practical application of these methods are well described. Ishmuhammedov R. "Ways to increase the effectiveness of education with the help of innovative technologies" and interactive methods. Avliyokulov M.Kh. Important methodological aspects are revealed in the manual "Modern teaching technologies". Jorayeva's A.S. The book "Interactive methods of education" also reveals important aspects of the methods. Also, a number of articles were published by Methodist scientists and advanced school teachers in the press and methodical journals. Among them, Safarova R., Gulomova M., Inoyatova M., Soliyeva M., in the article "Using interactive methods during literacy training" (in the case of didactic games) in the methodological manual "Literacy Teaching Lessons" specifically focuses on this issue and supports it with evidence. illuminates based on[4-5].

Full implementation of new pedagogical technologies in life, achieving the intended result directly depends on the effective performance of teachers. If the students' activity and their conscious observation are not ensured in any used method, no results can be achieved.

Ensuring not only physical, but also mental, spiritual and moral perfection of students in elementary grades, developing them by harmonizing educational content, teaching methods, tools and forms, and developing independent creative, analytical and critical thinking skills, to all aspects of the educational process, as well as this in the process, a conclusion is drawn about the need to create a creative environment. Preparation of various interactive methods for teaching historical subjects to students is a unique pedagogical problem, based on factors such as the teacher's desire for professional development, understanding the importance of innovation processes, understanding the content and logical necessity of changes and innovations[6].

Method is actually derived from the Greek word "methodos" which means "way of knowledge and research", "theory", "doctrine".

Methodology (country, "methodike") is a science of teaching methods, ways and tools, a collection of methods, methods or teaching methods for performing, implementing, fulfilling a work. For example, methods of languages, methods of arithmetic, etc[7].

Educational method is a method of work that a teacher regularly uses with students, which allows students to develop their intellectual abilities and interests, acquire knowledge and skills, and use them in practice. It is a set of organized ways of organizing the mutual activities of the teacher and the students in order to achieve the specified educational goal[8].

Knowledge of teaching methods, classification according to their sources is quite simple, and they are widespread in school practice. According to this sign, the methods are divided into the following three groups:

1. Verbal methods (verbal presentation of knowledge, conversation, working with textbooks and scientific literature).
2. Instructional methods (pictures, demonstrations, observations).
3. Practical methods (exercises, practical works in the laboratory).

By using interactive methods in teaching elementary school students, it is possible to achieve high efficiency of their learning activities. For this, primary school teachers themselves need to learn such methods. Interactive methods for elementary school students are one of the types of activating methods of learning, which form

students' independent thinking, oral and written communication skills. First of all, let's talk about the concepts of "interactive", "interactive education", "interactivity" and "interactive methods"[9].

The concept of "interactive" is expressed in English by the word "interact" ("interactive" in Russian), and from the dictionary point of view, it means "inter" - mutual, bilateral, "act" - to act, to do business. Interactive education is education based on the organization of action based on mutual cooperation of the participants of the educational process in order to acquire knowledge, skills, competences and certain moral qualities[10].

Interactivity is the ability of the participants of the educational process to organize action based on mutual cooperation in order to acquire knowledge, skills, competences and certain moral qualities.

Interactive methods are methods that provide interaction between the teacher and the learner, activate them and encourage them to think independently, and are aimed at increasing the motivation to learn.

Today's Uzbekistan has a rich historical source. Our grandfathers and grandmothers, who lived and worked in this holy soil, showed true heroism and protected their homeland from foreign invaders.

It is clear to everyone that the heroism of brave Tomaris amazes the whole world today. It is noteworthy that they bravely fought against Kaykhusrav, who wanted to dominate someone else's land, and fought against the enemy based on their heroism, bravery, justice, and most importantly, high discipline. Shiroq, a true patriot, showed an even higher example of heroism. Sacrificing his life for the great goal of protecting the motherland, he saved the land of his country, the property of his holy country, and his sons and daughters from the enemy.

One of the great scholars of the Uzbek nation, Abu Rayhan Beruni, gave insights into the various ways and means of imparting knowledge to the young generation in his works.

He focused on educating them to be independent thinkers and innovators. In the work "Monuments left by ancient peoples", Beruni emphasized the search for ways to increase the efficiency of learning, developing children's memory, and teaching them to think. The goal is not to stretch the sentence, but not to bore the reader, because always looking at the same thing leads to boredom and impatience. As the student moves from subject to subject, he seems to be walking in different gardens. Before you can see one, another begins, and as it is said that everything has its own

taste, he is interested in seeing them and wants to look at them. The same thing is tiring, boring to the memory"

The great general Amir Temur emphasized in his teachings that when starting any job, one should focus all his attention, intelligence and all his strength on it: "I worked with determination. If I set out to do something, I put all my mind and body into it, and I didn't take my hand off it until I finished it."

In his time, Amir Temur demanded that his subordinates be entrepreneurs, businessmen, like-minded, talkative, and shoulder-to-shoulder for the improvement of the country and peace of the nation.

The great thinker and great poet Alisher Navoi in his work "Mahbub ul-Qulub" evaluates the work of school teachers and explains that his work requires a lot of effort.

The analysis of the studied literature, as well as the educational practice, shows that the interest in the emergence, formation, and development of pedagogical ingenuity, striving for innovation is increasing more and more.

Elementary reading textbooks present passages on a number of historical topics, the study of which is fundamentally different from the study of works of art and excerpts from our lives today.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Yoqubov Sh. Zokirov J. "Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayoniga innovatsion yondashuv" respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari Termiz. 2019 (24-25 betlar)
2. Zokirov, J. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF STRENGTHENING LESSONS IN STUDENTS'MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY. Academic research in modern science, 1(9), 344-348.
3. O'g'li, Z. J. G. (2023). ONA TILI VA O'QISH SAVODXONLIGI DARSLARIDA KLASTER METODLARIDAN FOYDALANISH. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 4), 76-79.
4. Zokirov, J. G. O. (2023). ZAMONAVIY ONA TILI VA O'QISH SAVODXONLIGI FANINING YANGILANISHI, MAZMUNI VA AHAMIYATI. Academic research in educational sciences, 5(NUU conference 3), 90-96.
5. Зокиров, Д. (2022). Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darslarida matn ustida ishlash yo'llari. Современные тенденции инновационного развития науки и образования в глобальном мире, 1(2), 288-291.

6. Zokirov, J. (2023). SIFATLI TA'LIM BERISHDA ZAMONAVIY ONA TILI VA O'QISH SAVODXONLIGI DARSLIGINING ROLI. Interpretation and researches, 2(1).
7. Javohir G'aybullo o'g, Z. (2023). 1-3-Sinf O 'Quvchilariga Ona Tili Va O 'Qish Savodxonligi Fanidan Beriladigan Mashqlar Turlari. Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art, 2(2), 161-163.
8. Javohir G'aybullo o'g', Z. (2023). Boshlang'ich Sinf Ona Tili Va OQish Savodxonligi O'rgatish Usullari. Innovatsiyalar, ijodkorlik va san'at jurnali , 2 (2), 164-168.
9. ZOKIROV, J. (2022). BOSHLANG 'ICH SINIF ONA TILI DARSLIKLARIDA MASHQLARNING XUSUSIYATLARI. " ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ АКМЕОЛОГИЯ" международный научно-методический журнал, 2(2).
10. Javohir G'aybullo o'g, Z. (2023). Ona Tili Va OQish Savodxonligi Darslarida QoLlaniladigan Metodlarning Tasnifi. Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art, 2(2), 180-184.